

Description scientifique du projet

Titre du projet : Towards hybrid meta-modelling earthquake scenarios : improving high-fidelity numerical simulation with machine learning techniques.

Numéro du projet DARI¹ : A0060410444

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Nombre d'heures demandées (Cpu mono-processeur) sur le projet :

CINES BULL noeuds fins Occigen : 2.500.000 heures scalaires

1 Résumé

The objective of this project is to predict the dynamic behaviour of strategic structures (such as nuclear power plants) and to assess the seismic response of large seismic-prone urban areas, at the occurrence of extreme ground shaking events. To this end, we have recently developed an efficient multi-tool computational platform, capable of simulating broad-band non-linear seismic wave propagation in highly heterogeneous media, from the fault to the aboveground structures (i.e. at a regional scale). The core of the platform is represented by SEM3D, a Spectral Element (SE) Method code tailored to solve 3-D wave propagation in anisotropic, randomly heterogeneous and non-linear geo-materials. The platform efficiently handles the presence of complex surface topography, coastlines and bathymetry, 3-D geological configurations along with large fault discontinuities [[Gatti et al'2017a](#), [21](#), [24](#), [25](#), [26](#)]. The wave-propagation code has previously shown very good scalability in mesh featured by millions of hexahedral elements. For instance, we studied the seismic response of the Kashiwazaki-Kariwa Nuclear Power Plant (KKNPP), during the $M_W 6.6$ 2007 Niigata earthquake (central west-coast of Japan) reaching a maximum frequency f_{max} of 7 Hz, in a computational domain of $60 \text{ km} \times 60 \text{ km} \times 60 \text{ km}$, with a minimum grid size of $200 \text{ m} \times 200 \text{ m} \times 200 \text{ m}$, with minimal shear wave velocity of 700 m/s [[25](#)]. Similar earthquake

1. Uniquement en cas de demande de prolongation d'un projet existant.

2. Le responsable se charge du suivi du projet et fournit un bilan en fin d'année.

scenarios are currently being run for the Argostoli site (a European test site, where a vast geophysical and tectonic survey are currently carried out), within the framework of the ongoing A0040410444 call. The performances of SEM3D have been checked within this ongoing project (see activity report) : for the Argostoli test case, we managed to perform our largest physics-based high-fidelity numerical simulation of a main shock earthquake scenario, reliable up to a maximum frequency of 10 Hz, in the softest part of the domain (i.e. where shorter wave lengths must be correctly discretized).

However, real case studies are featured by very soft soil deposits (typically reaching values of 200 m/s), requiring higher spatial resolution for the same maximum frequency propagated (the Argostoli test case is featured by a minimum shear-wave velocity of 650 m/s). Furthermore, the modal response of rigid structures (for instance the reactor buildings) shifts towards higher frequencies (≥ 10 Hz), that should be excited by broad-band synthetic input motion (for instance, for a Soil-Structure Interaction model at the site scale). Finally, the possibility of modelling the heterogeneous spatial fluctuations and uncertainty of the input parameters in a non-linear wave propagation context (due to the development of a very efficient random field generator over large domains, coupled with SEM3D), permits the modelling of complex scattering effects taking place at higher frequencies (i.e. higher spatial resolutions) and leads to explore different realizations of the same earthquake scenario.

Therefore, we consider in this project an extension of the mentioned analyses (see, for instance, [25, 26, 27]). We have at least three tests cases in our disposal : the region surrounding the KKNPP, the Argostoli basin and the Volvi basin (another experimental site in Greece). This achievement will be exploited to improve probabilistic vulnerability assessment, using uncertainty propagation techniques (construction of meta-model simulations and fragility curves). As a matter of fact, high-fidelity earthquake simulations can be exploited to either construct brand-new site-specific databases including a great number of synthetic ground motions, either to integrate existing recording databases, to be exploited for several purposes. In other words, the results of the set of cumbersome simulations foreseen in this project will be a suitable basis for surrogate modelling (performed externally, in a posterior phase, by applying, for instance, machine learning techniques such as ANN2BB [29]), so as to reduce the computation time associated keeping an accurate prediction. However, in doing so, the experimental design (ED) is constructed by SEM3D analyses.

2 Présentation générale

For a long time, geophysicists have concentrated on wave propagation in *simplified* geological media (e.g. considering the Earth's crust as sub-horizontally layered visco-elastic half-space) neglecting crucial issues, such as :

- the heterogeneities in the Earth's crust (at regional and site scale)
- the non-linearity of shallow soil deposits
- the surface topography
- solid-fluid interaction (coastlines, bathymetry etc)

Although the mentioned numerical models were capable of reproducing reasonably well the P, S or Rayleigh waves arrival times and the main reflections within the Earth's crust, they were generally limited to the very low-frequency part of the radiated spectrum.

Moreover, very rare are the examples of a continuous fault-to-structure interaction studies. The most reliable and efficient method was proposed by Bielak et al. [8], called the Domain Reduction Method. It consists into a two-step analysis, declined as follows : (i) regional scale wave-propagation in simplified geological medium (typically the deep visco-elastic stratified Earth's crust), not including the non-linear site-effects ; (ii) a second run of the analysis on a smaller domain (eventually adding the structure) delimited by an artificial boundary at which equivalent inertial forces and free-field velocities, obtained in the precedent step, are applied. Quinay et al. [13] applied this method to study the structural response of the Kashiwazaki-Kariwa Nuclear Power Plant (KKNPP) in a fault-to-structure framework, up to 1 Hz.

Those aspects clashes with the need of broad-band realistic synthetics to input into realistic structural models : the transient dynamics of above-ground structures (eventually with soil-structure interaction at the site scale) has been traditionally studied separately, by employing selected spectrum-compatible recordings. In any case, the seismic design of critical structures requires refined analyses providing synthetic ground motion time-histories reliable at higher frequencies and reproducing complex phenomena such as the coda in the seismic signals [2], the directivity and the incoherence of the wave motion near-source [24], the non-linear site effects [20].

The ever increasing availability of computer power paves the way to deterministic exploration of the scenarios space, compatibly with the degree of knowledge of focal issues, such as :

1. the 3-D geological structure of the Earth's crust
2. the geomechanical properties of soil deposits and deep bedrock

3. the surface morphology (topography, bathymetry, coastlines)
4. the characteristics of the active faults (tectonic context, slip patches, focal mechanisms)

The level of uncertainty related to this piece of information, convolved together with the numerical dispersion, determines its predictive fidelity of such physics-based analyses. Researchers are trying to address those issues, mainly through full-waveform inversion [16, 22], noise correlations [Book Fouque et al 2008 Wave Pro], probabilistic models of the fluctuations [6, 7], complex rheological models.

In this project, instead, we try to employ the efficient multi-tool platform developed so far to reproduce numerically those observations, when considering high resolution wave propagation problem using conformal hexahedra, which are necessary for the widely used spectral finite element method [Komatitsch Tromp I 2002, 5, 9]. Moreover, we aim at calibrating those models with the structural dynamics counterpart [13], for forward vulnerability assessment. Here, high resolution means meshes containing billions of elements [11, 14, 15]. Performing wave propagation in such meshes becomes a possibility through the unprecedented development of powerful computational resources and scalable parallel solvers. However, constructing efficiently such discretizations and running the simulations on such meshes is not an easy task. Recently some research groups have shattered the barrier of running analyses on very large meshes, exhausting all resources on very large machines all over the world. An impressive result was obtained by a Chinese research group, who run a non-linear earthquake simulation over a continental 320 km by 312 km by 40 km region, up to 18 Hz [19]. The use of octrees has made possible a high degree of scalability in mesh generation using up to 220.000 cores [11].

To tackle the mentioned obstacles, recently, we have developed a series of computational tools that help in constructing large scale numerical scenario of an earthquake event, namely :

- a numerical technique that allows to generate conformal hexahedral meshes using an octree-based method similar to [12] ;
- an efficient random field generator over large computational domains [28], based on a fully parallelized version of the spectral representation technique [4] ;
- a parallel non-linear wave-propagation solver based on the spectral element method and coupled with the random field generator [21].

The parallel octree-based mesh generator is able to treat immersed geometries with high scalability in executions. It was tested up to 6561 processing cores. The mesh can be non-conformal, composed exclusively by hexahedral elements, or it can be made conformal using tetrahedral elements. Non-

conforming meshes have hanging nodes, (i.e. nodes located inside edges or faces), which restricts its use to numerical methods that provide support for this type of nodal interpolation. In particular, efficient parallel implementation of the SE Method (SEM) requires the use of conformal hexahedra. Owing to the SEM spectral convergence, higher resolution is obtained by p -refinement (i.e. by increasing the polynomial order) rather than by increasing the number of linear elements (common practice in Finite Difference/Element schemes).

The random field generator employs the sum of a series of N_ϕ cosines with random phases/amplitudes [4], sampled over fine regular grids [21]. The Fast Fourier Transform can be used to bring the complexity of this generation method to $\mathcal{O}(N_\phi \log N_\phi)$. The field is then re-interpolated over the not uniformly space-distributed SE grid (featured by 5 to 10 Gauss-Lobatto-Legendre points per dimension). When dealing with large domains, the scalability issue is solved by generating smaller independent realizations, supported on overlapping subdomains (in a distributed memory parallel scheme), and then recomposed together into the full domain.

Finally, the non-linear wave-propagation solver exploits the high resolution of the spectral element method with efficient explicit algorithm to integrate non-linear rheology representing the non-linear cyclic behaviour of soils.

3 Méthode

3.1 Méthode numérique

The computational platform we are intended to test in this project bares upon three numerical codes :

- SEM3D : an efficient Spectral Element code tailored for wave-propagation in non-linear heterogeneous geo-materials at the regional and continental scales [21] ;
- HexMesh³ : a scalable octree-based mesh generation code ;
- randomField⁴ : a scalable random field generator over large computational domains, based on the spectral generation technique [3].

The first code is the center of our attention in this project and has already run efficiently on large scale machines, reproducing real earthquake scenarios with high accuracy. The second and third codes are used in conjunction with the spectral element code, so to mesh correctly the complex morphology of the Earth's crust structure and its rheology with natural spatial fluctuations.

3. <https://github.com/jcamata/HexMesh.git>

4. <https://github.com/cottureau/randomField.git>

Non-linear wave propagation : SEM3D

We develop SEM3D [18] jointly by the Institut de Physique du Globe de Paris, CEA and CentraleSupélec, mainly for applications in geophysics, with the aim of considering realistic 3-D complex geo-structures. It is written in Fortran 95, and uses MPI. The I/O is performed using parallel HDF5 libraries. The meshes are non-structured and composed of conformal hexahedra by employing METIS⁵ library. The discretization in space is based on spectral elements in space and an explicit scheme in time (both for elastic and non-linear case). The spectral element method is a variant of the finite element methods which uses high-order Lagrange polynomials on Gauss-Lobatto-Legendre (GLL) points. The corresponding quadrature ensures that the mass matrix is diagonal. Hence, inversion of the mass matrix at each time steps is not costly and very short time steps, imposed by the explicit scheme, are not an issue. The code was tested on several clusters, including Curie (by CEA) and the Mésocentre de CentraleSupélec and ENS Paris Saclay (SGI ICE X) and GENCI Occigen (c20150447417 and the ongoing A4 allocation project A0040410444). Moreover, it has been run on the 64-nodes Bi-Opteron cluster of Service de Calcul Parallèle de l’Institut de Physique du Globe de Paris (a model with 25 millions degrees of freedom, running over 128 cores). A previous version of the code (less efficient in terms of parallelism [23]) was tested on Jade, in a previous GENCI project (c2010046485). On these occasions, the weak scalability of the spectral element solver has been demonstrated. Finally, it should be noted that a code with similar features and structure (although developed by a completely different team) was ported on the largest clusters available (see for example [9], 15 years back). An example of weak scalability curve obtained for SEM3D is shown in Figure 1. SEM3D has been run over more than 4096 cores. Moreover, given the experience of allocation A4 (with mid-term correction), a comparison between SEM3D performances obtained on FUSION (cluster of Mésocentre Moulon) and OCCIGEN were compared between each other, to check our estimations in terms of required CPU-hours. The numerical models of the Niigata earthquake (scenario 1) and Argostoli basin (scenario 2) were exploited. Ten simulations are hereafter compared : F1-F5, run on FUSION, O1-O5, run on OCCIGEN (see the specifics in Table 1). Fig. 2 shows the performances obtained, compared to the original (CP) and corrected-blind (BP) prediction (made before allocation A4). First and foremost, we noticed a very good agreement between the corrected prediction CP and F1 and BP and F4, which justifies our prediction made on FUSION. However, we needed some preliminary iterations (corresponding to simula-

5. <http://glaros.dtc.umn.edu/gkhome/views/metis>

Figure 1 – Weak scalability curves obtained for SEM3D, expressed as number of time rate of mesh elements processed varying the number of MPI process employed. In blue, the linear scalability curve represents the ideal *optimum* result (perfectly linear scalability). Green and red lines portray the *worst* and *average* performances instead.

tions O1-O3) to replicate the same performances obtained on FUSION (in terms of CPU-time). Specifically, preliminary simulations O1-O3 (performed without the CINES support, before the mid-term allocation) showed an increased computation burden (expressed as t_{CPU}/t_{EQK}). For instance, O2 and F4 represents the same simulation, although we obtained a CPU-time per second real time simulation $t_{CPU}/t_{EQ} [h/s]$ of 1.82×10^3 h/s for FUSION and 3.49×10^4 h/s for OCCIGEN respectively. Iteration O4 was performed thanks to the CINES support : the same performances were obtained for FUSION and OCCIGEN on the same test case. This iteration validates SEM3D portability on OCCIGEN and allowed us to obtain mid-term extra hour allocations. In the following, we transitioned towards a higher number of DOFs by improving the numerical model of Argostoli (including the new code feature represented by the extended fault seismic source) previously run on FUSION (F5). On OCCIGEN, the same numerical model was considered (called O5), its accuracy being increased by p -refinement, i.e. by increasing two times the GLL points per edge (resulting in $10 \times 10 \times 10$ GLL points per element), for a total $\approx 13.48 \cdot 10^9$. Expected performances were attained (quasi-linear scalability) and we successfully passed the limit of 10^{10} DOFs (never before achieved on FUSION), thanks to the possibility of running jobs over > 720 CPU - cores (current limitation for FUSION).

Figure 2 – CPU-time per real earthquake simulation t_{CPU}/t_{EQK} , for different DOF numbers. BP and CP correspond to the blind and corrected-blind predictions respectively (see mid-term allocation).

	N_{EL}	N_{GLL}	N_{MPI}
F1	2×10^6	5	648
F2	-	7	648
F3	-	10	648
F4	18×10^6	5	648
F5	4.5×10^6	5	216
O1	-	5	4800
O2	-	5	648
O3	-	7	648
O4	-	5	4800
O5	4.5×10^6	5	4000
CP	2×10^6	5	216
BP	18×10^6	5	648

Table 1 – Earthquake numerical model. N_E : number of hexaedrael elements (8-nodes); N_{GLL} : number of GLL points per element); N_{MPI} : number of CPU cores.

Octree-based Mesh Generation : HexMesh

Octrees are hierarchical data structures that allows the decomposition a three-dimensional space in regular cubes, called octants. The initial octant normally surrounds all the input domain and is divided in 8 equally spaced cubes - the child octants. Each of these children could be subdivided again, in a recursive process that is usually limited by some criteria (i.e. maximum number of subdivisions, minimum octant size). An octree can be implemented by a tree structure or by a linear octree, where only octants with no children are stored. In this last representation, as also known by linear octree, each leaf is stored as a unique integer - called locational code - which identifies its position and depth level in the tree. Among the benefits of linear octrees is the implicit representation of intermediary octants (non-leaves), making it memory efficient, and better performance on sequential access. Additionally, by not making use of memory pointers, parallel implementation of the linear octree has a lower overhead in interprocess communication (in comparison to other tree structures [10]). We have implemented a set of algorithms that address the special needs of parallel octree meshing. These algorithms are : (i) Octree initialization algorithm that guarantees that all processes have at least one piece of the linear octree. (ii) Refinement algorithm that decompose

the octants according to some refinement criterion (i.e. maximum size or position relative to the geometry boundaries), and 2 :1 balancing algorithm that ensure that no neighbor octants differentiate in more than one level [10]. This last algorithm is important because a balanced octree results in more smooth transitions between elements, a feature that has a direct influence on the final mesh quality. It also guarantees that the resulting mesh will not have more than one hanging node for each edge or face, reducing the complexity of conforming mesh process. The resulting code has been written in plain C and makes use of MPI only. The code runs on any standard cluster. A previous version of the code (generating non-conformal hexahedra and conformal tetrahedra meshes) has been tested at Stampede Dell cluster (at TACC) and on a SGI ICE 8400 and on a Oracle cluster in Brazil. Table 2 presents a weak scalability test performed on the mesh of the Kefalonia region (Greece). The communication time (last column) attains a fairly constant percentage of the total time. The code has run over 6561 MPI cores.

Cores	Levels	Nodes	Elements	Time (s)	Comm(%)
81	7	85,602,744	83,102,679	12.061	21 %
243	8	769,790,232	747,937,476	32.994	20 %
729	9	6,926,153,724	6,731,438,013	105.188	25 %
6561	10	62,330,385,168	60,583,119,264	123.066	29 %

Table 2 – Weak scaling of the mesh generation for the Kefalonia region in Greece. Cores : number of MPI cores ; Levels : octree refinement level ; Nodes : number of mesh nodes ; Elements : number of mesh elements ; Time : generation time ; Comm : percentage of the total elapsed time for communication operation.

Random Field Generation : randomFields

The heterogeneous properties of the Earth’s crust are included in our modelling strategy for large scale earthquake scenarios. In this context, by *large* we refer to a domain size L much larger than both the correlation length ℓ_C (or some characteristic size of the fluctuation) and the discretization step h . It is therefore advantageous to represent those fluctuations a scalar random fields (for instance, representing the spatial distribution of the shear-modulus). Those large random fields can be effectively sampled over a coarse grid (with a step size relevant for the correlation length) and then interpolated onto the mesh of interest (provided by the GLL (Gauss-Lobatto-Legendre) grid used in SEM3D). If the discretization step is much larger than the correlation length, the sampling becomes simple and numerically inexpensive. Indeed, for the mesh considered, the random field is

essentially a white noise with Gaussian first-order marginal density [17]. The first-order marginal density is modified locally by combining a direct and inverse Rosenblatt transforms [1]. `randomField` uses the spectral quadrature formula proposed by [4] to generate the random field, taking advantage of the Fast Fourier Transform algorithms (using the library FFTW⁶). The code is written in Fortran95 and exploits HDF5 data structures for I/O operations. To efficiently reduce the generation time for large L/ℓ_C values, `randomField` is implemented in a highly-scalable *localized* fashion, exploiting MPI. Independent realizations are generated over subdomains, that are then recomposed into the whole domain, by smoothing the discontinuities at the boundaries between partitions to preserve the correlation structure.

Table 3 lists the results of the scalability test performed on `randomField`, with the *standard* and *localized* approaches respectively (i.e. by generating a unique random field over the entire domain (*standard* approach) or by generating independent realizations over subdomains (*localized* approach)). This scalability test was performed by running the generation code on OCCIGEN cluster.

Cores	Nodes	Generation Time (s)	
		Standard	Localized
16	1×10^6	0.86	6.57
32	2×10^6	1.55	13.87
256	2×10^7	356.43	159.98
2048	1×10^8	–	2037.48
4096	3×10^8	–	3299.04

Table 3 – Weak scalability analysis for the random field generation (Machine : OCCIGEN Intel E5-2690 (2.6 GHz) / $\sim 50 \times 10^3$ cores). Standard : wall-time required to generate a single random field over the entire domain. Localized : wall-time time required to generate the random field with the localized approach mentioned in the text.

The information above mentioned testifies the efficiency and scalability of the computational platform we aim at exploiting, conformingly with the performances required to submit this project.

6. <http://fftw.org/>

3.2 Justification de l’emploi de la machine demandée

We will focus here on a few simulations of earthquake scenarios at regional scale. The reference test case is O5 simulation (see Table 1). For this simulation, ≈ 81100 hours CPU-time were necessary (≈ 20 hours wall-time, on 4000 MPI-cores). To have an idea of the machine allocation required, some information related to the O5 simulations are reported in Table 4 and Table 5. Table 5 lists the computational resources employed to perform the

N_E	N_D	$\mathcal{L}_x \times \mathcal{L}_y \times \mathcal{L}_z [km^3]$	$\Delta_x^{min} \times \Delta_y^{min} \times \Delta_z^{min} [m^3]$
$\approx 4.5 \cdot 10^6$	$\approx 1.68 \cdot 10^9$	$44 \times 44 \times 63$	$130 \times 130 \times 35$

Table 4 – Mesh characteristics for the earthquake scenario of Kefalonia island [31] (model O5). N_E : number of hexaedrael elements (8-nodes); N_D : number of Degrees of Freedom ($10 \times 10 \times 10$ GLL points per element); \mathcal{L}_x - \mathcal{L}_y - \mathcal{L}_z domain sizes; Δ_x^{min} - Δ_y^{min} - Δ_z^{min} minimum element sizes.

simulation described, for 20.0 seconds of real earthquake. Please note that the scalar computational time t_{CPU} indicated in Table 5 represents the total elapsed CPU time as equivalent mono-processor, i.e. it is the sum of the running times of each processor (in the presented case, 4000 MPI processors), according to the equation :

$$t_{CPU} = t_{wall} \times N_{MPI} \quad (1)$$

where t_{wall} is the wall-time (also called *elapsed* time) and N_{MPI} is number of MPI processes.

N_{MPI}	$M_{MPI} [Gb]$	$t_{CPU} [h]$	$HD [Gb]$	N_{FILES}
4000	1	≈ 81100	≈ 3500	≈ 15000

Table 5 – Computational resources allocated for one simulation of the Argostoli earthquake scenario. N_{MPI} : number of MPI processes; M_{MPI} : memory per MPI process; t_{CPU} mono-processor equivalent CPU-time (for 20.0 seconds of real earthquake) computed as $walltime \times N_{MPI}$ (see Eq. 1); HD : Hard-Disk allocation; N_{FILES} : number of files generated.

The HD in Table 5 refers to the total storage required for : (1) saving results (typically, 1000 Gb for velocity contour maps close to the surface topography, 5 Gb for the time histories), (2) storing mesh files and heterogeneous mechanical properties (≈ 10 -20 Gb) and to perform save&restart procedure (state variables must be saved all over the domain, which leads to around ≈ 2000 Gb). All files saved are in HDF5 format. The amount of

file generated N_{FILES} includes the protections, that are immediately erased after the run, and the mesh files, which are the same for each simulation.

In this project, we will investigate some realizations of an earthquake scenarios (chosen between three available test cases). Given the performances presented so far and aiming at pushing the frequency limit towards 10 Hz, with reduced shear wave-velocities, two strategies can be pursued : (1) p -refinement (i.e. increasing the polynomial order) or (2) h -refinement (i.e. decrease the mesh element size). Owing to preliminary heuristic calculations, however, we are inclined to refine the mesh element size locally by keeping a lower polynomial order (h -refinement). Table 6 describes the details of the calculations we aim at performing. For this, we demand 2500000 scalar hours (CPU-time) and we aim at performing simulations over 4800 cores average (200 nodes bi-processor Intel Xeon Haswell - 2.6 Ghz).

Supported by the test performed so far, the estimations provided in Table 6 are based on a computational grid with an estimated number of DOFs of $\approx 2 \cdot 10^{10}$ and for simulations of 20 seconds of real earthquake. Therefore the t_{CPU} ⁷=81100 h computed for 4000 MPI cores in Table 5 allow us to run around 30 simulations with the same layout/settings of O5, so to be able to have a statistically consistent amount of scenarios to perform Probabilistic Seismic Hazard Assessment and train Artificial Neural Network algorithms employed as earthquake simulation meta-models. This amount is consistent with the work of Paolucci et al. [30], who performed 30 simulation of the Istanbul area (Turkey). The difference between scenarios will mainly consist into : different seismic source configurations and different statistical realization of the natural heterogeneous geology of the Earth’s crust (see initial proposal). In terms of memory, we need to save approximately 1500 Gb of the

Case Study	N_S	t_{CPU} [h]	N_{MPI}	N_{FILES}
Argostoli basin (Greece)	30	81100	4096	15000

Table 6 – Set of foreseen simulations for the project proposal. The Argostoli basin is taken as reference. N_S : number of simulations per test case (30 in total); t_{CPU} : mono-processor equivalent CPU-time per each run, computed as $walltime \times N_{MPI}$ (see Eq. 1); N_{MPI} : number of cores MPI employed per run; N_{FILES} : number of file generated per run.

actual 3500 Gb demanded per run (we erase the protections). Therefore we estimated 30 Tb maximum of hard-disk allocation (data will be progressively

⁷. mono-processor equivalent CPU-time per each run, computed as $walltime \times$ number of processors, see Eq. 1

repatriated).

4 Bibliographie

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